

Youth Empowerment and Sustainable Development: An Assessment of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ Scheme in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Youth empowerment and development can be achieved through adequate training and empowerment. Perhaps governments implement different programmes to empower their young generation with this in mind.

Objective: This study investigates the effect of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme on youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Methodology: The study adopted a quantitative research design. A purposive random sampling technique was used to select the targeted respondents. Data was sourced through questionnaire

copies and participant observation and presented and analysed using inferential statistics, such as frequency tables, mean, and chi-square, to test the hypotheses.

Results: The study found that the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has significantly influenced youth empowerment and sustainable development. An effective transformational leadership style with clearly set goals and good management has helped achieve this. However, insufficient funds, unequal distribution of materials and allocations, and poor monitoring and supervision, among other challenges, are affecting the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State.

Conclusion: To ensure a strong youth orientation towards economic empowerment and growth, a serious partnership is needed to ensure inclusive policies that invest in youth training.

Unique Contribution: This study contributes to the existing literature on the best practices and modalities for ensuring effective youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra, Nigeria.

Key Recommendations: To attain the aim of empowerment, an increase in funds/grants, equitable allocation of resources and materials, more partnerships, collaboration, proper monitoring, and mentorship are needed.

Keywords: One Youth-Two Skills, Scheme, sustainable development, youth empowerment, Anambra, Nigeria.

Introduction

The world is actively shaped by the mass number of youth, estimated at 1.45 billion between 18 and 29, who comprise the largest youth generation in history. In addition to being passionate about enacting change, they are also increasingly pushing social, political, and economic advancement within and beyond their local communities (UNDP, 2024). Youth are inherently highly vivacious and trustworthy change agents; any society hoping to grow must acknowledge that its youth require more significant economic, political, and social-cultural influence. The youth saw a society free from discrimination based on race, ethnicity, gender, or language, one that was full of opportunities and obstacles to conquer and one that was devoid of poverty, unemployment, inequality, and human exploitation. Youth development and empowerment have emerged as a primary concern in Africa. Because of this, African social, political, and economic systems have frequently experienced unrest and instability, issues ascribed to different social groups and people (Chiedozie & Joshua, 2015).

The risk of unemployment and inactivity is particularly evident as most young people live on the streets, needing work to survive. When there are no jobs available, some of these young people turn to social vices like drug and crime abuse. The youth’s role in any society is crucial. Although they can drive and promote economic and national development, they remain the nation’s most hated, undervalued, and underutilised group (Ibrahim, 2002). However, youth in Nigeria strive to play a role in national development like other youths in developing countries. Investigating the underlying causes of this complicated problem, academics have painstakingly found that low levels of education, historical antecedents, and unfavourable economic circumstances are all significant contributors to violence and instability throughout Africa (Joshua, et al., 2021).

Youth worldwide are still marginalised and silenced by outmoded conventions, depriving them of their rights and vital role in forming and carrying out laws and choices that impact on them and

future generations. Therefore, several issues like exposure to insecurity, unemployment, poverty, lack of access to good healthcare, etc., have prevented Nigerian youth from realising their potential. Consequently, social unrest, agitation and increased crime are inevitable among youths who are unemployed and unskilled in their prime (Ezebuilo, 2023). Thus, many challenges have existed to impede youth empowerment and development schemes.

Youth empowerment is a significant issue in many developing countries, like Nigeria, where youth unemployment is a concern. The youth of Anambra State confront restricted employment possibilities, low-skill development, and socio-economic marginalisation. Despite government intervention efforts, youth empowerment remains a significant issue hindering socio-economic and sustained development. Therefore, on this premise, this study assesses the impact of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ solution empowerment scheme on sustainable youth development in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study raised the following questions:

- a. How has the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme impacted youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State?
- b. What strategies has the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme adopted to achieve youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State?
- c. What challenges affect the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ youth scheme in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses (Ho) were put forward for the test:

- a. The ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme does not significantly impact Anambra State’s youth empowerment and sustainable development.
- b. The ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has no strategies for achieving youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State.
- c. There are no challenges facing the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme on youth empowerment and development at Anambra State.

Literature Review

Youth Empowerment

Empowerment is the ability to achieve something or, maybe more accurately, the process of growing more robust and self-assured, particularly in taking charge of one’s life and asserting one’s rights (Nataro, 2022). Empowerment” is a strategy that can bring about growth and development at the social, political, economic and individual levels. The notion of empowerment greatly influences the definition of “youth empowerment,” as it is employed in this work. Empowering young people to feel a sense of belonging and contribute to society’s sustainable

development involves giving them access to political, economic, intellectual, and social power (Aquino, 2018).

Youth empowerment is one of the empowerment movements that starts, grows, becomes sustainable, and eventually becomes institutionalised (Hackman & Johnson, 2016). Youth empowerment involves motivating them to take responsibility for their lives. They accomplish this by acknowledging their predicament, after which they take steps to enhance their resources and influence their awareness using their attitudes, core values, and beliefs. Thus, youth empowerment allows youth to harness and develop their abilities, inner potential, and self-assurance toward contributing to sustainable national development. Youth empowerment allows young people to take the lead, make decisions alongside their communities, and take control of their lives and futures. Improving every young person's quality of life is the primary goal of youth empowerment, irrespective of their gender, sexual orientation, religion, tribe, handicap, or socio-economic status (Child Hope, 2023).

Youth Development

According to the United States Department of Education (2007), Youth development is a gradual and comprehensive process that connotes many growth levels, helping youth acquire essential skills and values. The concept of development is multivariate. Rodney (1972) asserts that "In human civilisation, "development" refers to a multifaceted process that, at the individual level, entails improved ability and aptitude in addition to greater autonomy, imagination, restraint, accountability, and financial prosperity while social group development suggests a growing ability to control both internal and exterior relationships, i.e. development encompasses many strategies for transforming the socioeconomic and environmental landscape from existing states to desired ones.

Asirifi (2018) sees development as an intricate process with numerous components, including alterations to national organisations, cultural norms, and societal structures and eradicating absolute poverty. The dichotomy between youth empowerment and development is that youth empowerment aims to create broader community change via individual capacity development. In contrast, the goal of youth development is to develop people. However, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) asserts that including sports in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is one of the best concepts for empowering youth. Acquiring knowledge and skills, such as entrepreneurship, technical skill acquisition and innovation assistance, are crucial to youth empowerment (World Bank, 2007).

Emergence of the 'One Youth-Two Skills' Scheme

The Executive Governor of Anambra State, His Excellency Prof. Charles Chukwuma Soludo (CFR), introduced the 'One Youth-Two Skills'. This scheme was passed by the state House of Assembly into law in March 2022 to empower the youth in the State. This is done by providing them with the skills, tools, and resources needed to achieve their potential. This is the Anambra State 2070 plan, i.e. a plan to implement a community-based approach towards youth

empowerment and development, which will benefit the youth (Anambra State Ministry of Youth Development, 2023).

The ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ empowerment and development scheme was flagged off to create employment/jobs and skill acquisitions and make fewer than 1000 youth millionaires yearly (Anambra State Ministry of Youth Development, 2023). The scheme has engaged and empowered about 5,000 youths in 23 skill areas of interest in the pilot phase. It is a yearly designed empowerment scheme that engages non-indigenes and National Youth Corp Service (NYSC) members from various States across Nigeria undergoing compulsory one-year service in Anambra State. Nevertheless, the scheme was designed to help the youth gain the necessary skills to launch their businesses and secure jobs, i.e. it aims to provide each youth with at least two valuable and employable skills. The scheme aims to mitigate the menace caused by unemployment, such as armed robbery, kidnapping, violence, touting, prostitution, drug abuse, and criminality, among other social vices perpetrated by the youths, as this scheme has engaged them for a quality and productive work output (Anambra State Ministry of Youth Development, , 2023).

Nevertheless, the youth beneficiaries were grouped into tens to enable them to source the extra funds and loans to increase their capacity through Anambra State Business Agency (ASBA), which is on a single-digit repayment plan. The Anambra State Government has collaborated and partnered with organisations and institutions of ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ as follows: the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Anambra State Business Agency (ASBA), Entrepreneurship Development Institute (EDI), Nnamdi Azikiwe University Business School (NAUBS), Anambra State, IDK Learning Centre, Awka, Industrial Training Fund (ITF), Federal Polytechnic Oko (OKOPOLY), and Communities and Local Government Areas in the state etc. (Anambra State Government, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

Human Capital theory was adopted as this study’s framework of analysis. Theodore W. Schultz presented the Human Capital hypothesis in 1961. A person's degree of education and training determines their pay; the more qualified and skilled someone is, the higher their chances of landing a better job. The theory is based on the idea that individuals invest in themselves as “human capital” by acquiring skills and knowledge, and this investment can lead to economic growth. The theory has been relevant in addressing economic policy and is used to explain differences in financial performance, i.e., this theory implies a physical means of production (Becker, 1964).

Human Capital Theory (HCT), a rich history, posits that individuals can increase their productivity and income by investing in themselves through vocational education, training, and experience (Becker, 1964). This theory views people as investments that can generate returns on their capital and significantly contribute to the field (Schultz, 1961). Human capital theory has drawn criticism for its communication style and ignores the role of institutions in shaping economic outcomes. Institutions like legal, political, and educational systems can significantly impact individuals’ ability to develop their skills and knowledge and achieve financial success.

In application, the theory examines how investing in human capital development might boost the economy. The abilities, knowledge, and skills of people are referred to as human capital. Accordingly, the human capital theory predicts that raising people’s levels of expertise and ability through the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ boosts economic productivity in Anambra State. The human capital theory is apt for this study because it highlights the importance of employees’ skills, knowledge, and abilities (SKA) to the organisation’s effectiveness. As a result, proper planning is required to bring in the right “hands” and ensure the organisation never runs out of human capital (Eneanya, 2024).

Materials and Methods

A descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. The youth in Anambra state was targeted as the study population but was limited to those in Ogbaru, Onitsha North and South LGA. A mixed method of data was used, i.e. data was sourced from primary via structured questionnaires and participant observation and secondary via Scopus-indexed and Web of Science databases. Data was presented and analysed using inferential statistical analysis of frequency table, mean, and chi-square in testing the hypotheses. The study adopted a purposeful random sampling technique and a sample size of one hundred and fifty (150) youth participants for the data. A five-point Likert summated scaling method was used to address the structured questionnaires for the respondents to answer. The collected data were analysed using SPSS, which includes the frequency tables, straightforward percentages, statistical mean, and chi-square to test the hypothesis at a significant level of 0.05 (5%).

Data Presentation and Analysis

The research data was collected using a questionnaire distributed to one hundred and fifty (150) respondents across all the local government areas under study, of which one hundred and twenty (120) were returned. Therefore, the data was analysed using 120 respondents, and the results are presented below:

Table 1: Respondents Gender and Marital Status

a. Gender		Percentage	b. Marital Status		Percentage
Male	78	78%	Married	37	37%
Female	42	42%	Single	67	67%
Anonymous	0	0%	Anonymous	11	11%
Total	120	100%	Divorced	5	5%
			Total	120	100%

Source: *Authors’ Field Survey Result, (2025).*

The table shows that in **1a** and **1b**, among the 120 respondents who answered the research questionnaire, the males are 78%, females are 42%, and those who are anonymous about their gender status remain at 0%. However, the married respondents are 37%, the single ones are 67%, 11% are anonymous on their marital status, and the divorced ones are at 5%.

Table 2: Participants' LGA, Educational Background and Age

a. LGA		Percentage	b. Educational Background		Percentage	c. Age		Percentage
Ogbaru	44	44%	SSCE	44	41%	18-24	47	47%
Onitsha North	36	36%	ND/NCE	31	31%	25-34	40	40%
Onitsha South	40	40%	BSC/HND	38	38%	35-44	33	33%
Total	120	100%	PGD/MSC/PHD	7	7%	55-64	0	0%
			Others	0	0%	65&above	0	0%
			Total	120	100%	Total	120	100%

Source: *Authors' Field Survey Result (2025).*

The table shows that in **2a**, out of the 120 people who participated in answering the research questionnaire, 44% are from Ogbaru, 36% are from Onitsha North, and 40% are from Onitsha South L.G.As.; thus, in **2b**, 44% are SSCE holders, 31% are ND/NCE holders, 38% are BSC/HND holders while 7% are PGD/MSC/PHD holders. However, in **2c**, between 18-24 years are 47%, 25-34 years are 40%, 35-44 years old are 33%, while 55-64 and 65 years and above are at 0%.

Table 3: Participants' responses to the research questionnaire one (1): How has the 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme impacted youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State?

Questions	Effect Scale (%)					ΣFX	X= $\frac{\Sigma FX}{N}$
	SA (5)	A (4)	UN (3)	D (2)	SD (1)		
1. The 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme has affected your overall well-being, prospects and sustainable youth empowerment and development in Anambra State	66 (330)	33 (132)	8 (24)	9 (18)	4 (4)	120 508	4.2
2. The 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme has impacted on your ability to start and sustain your business or entrepreneurial venture.	57 (285)	44 (176)	6 (18)	5 (10)	8 (8)	120 497	4.1
3. The 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme has increased your skill acquisition, capacity, knowledge and employability.	61 (305)	35 (140)	8 (24)	6 (12)	10 (10)	120 491	4.0

Source: *Authors' Field Survey Result, (2025).*

In the analysis above, questionnaire item 1 has 66 respondents who strongly agreed, 33 agreed, 8 undecided, 9 disagreed, and 4 strongly disagreed; item 2 has 57 respondents who strongly agreed, 44 agreed, 6 undecided, 5 disagreed and 8 strongly disagreed while; item 3 has 61 respondents as strongly agreed, 35 agreed, 8 undecideds, 6 disagreed, and 10 strongly disagreed.

Table 4: Participants’ responses to the research questionnaire two (2): What strategies have the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme adopted to achieve youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State?

Questions	Effect Scale (%)					ΣFX	$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum FX}{N}$
	SA (5)	A (4)	UN (3)	D (2)	SD (1)		
4. Effective transformational leadership with clear set goals, objectives, and good management has aided the success of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme.	59 (295)	47 (188)	10 (30)	2 (4)	2 (2)	120 519	4.3
5. Adequate funding and resource allocation have contributed to the success of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme.	51 (255)	48 (192)	12 (36)	5 (10)	4 (4)	120 497	4.1
6. Partnership and collaborations with stakeholders and institutions have helped the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme.	60 (300)	37 (148)	15 (45)	3 (6)	5 (5)	120 504	4.2

Source: Authors’ Field Survey Result, (2025).

The analysis of questionnaire item 4 has respondents of 59 strongly agreed, 47 agreed, 10 undecideds, 2 disagreed, and 2 strongly disagreed; item 5 has 51 as strongly agreed, 48 agreed, 12 undecideds, 5 disagreed, and 4 strongly disagreed while item 6 has 60 as strongly agreed, 37 agreed, 15 undecideds, 3 disagreed, and 5 strongly disagreed.

Table 5: Participants’ responses to the research questionnaire three (3): What challenges affect the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ youth scheme in Anambra State?

Questions	Effect Scale (%)					ΣFX	$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum FX}{N}$
	SA (5)	A (4)	UN (3)	D (2)	SD (1)		
Research Question 3	75 (375)	25	11	6 (12)	3 (3)		

7. Insufficient funds and material allocation reduce the long-term sustainability of the 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme.		(100)	(33)			120 523	4.3
8. Inadequate partnerships and collaboration with private sector organisations and institutions inhibit the 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme.	58 (290)	49 (147)	5 (15)	4 (8)	4 (4)	120 464	3.8
9. Lack of qualified/professional master's trainers and proper monitoring affects the sustainability of the 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme.	68 (340)	40 (160)	7 (21)	3 (6)	2 (2)	120 529	4.4

Source: *Authors' Field Survey Result, (2025).*

The analysis of questionnaire item 7, which has responses of 75 strongly agreed, 25 agreed, 11 undecided, 6 disagreed, and 3 strongly disagreed; item 8 has 58 strongly agreed, 49 agreed, 5 undecided, 4 disagreed, and 4 strongly disagreed while; item 9 has 68 as strongly agreed, 40 agreed, 7 undecided, 3 disagreed, and 2 strongly disagreed.

The **Chi-square (X²)** formula is:

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

Where; \sum = Summation or Total Number
 f_o = Observed Frequency
 f_e = Expected Frequency

The Chi-square table value (X²) formula:

$$df = k - 1$$

d.f = Degree of Frequency
 K = Total Number of Response Options
 The Level of Significance is = 0.05
 $d.f = 5 - 1 = 4$
 $X^2 = 0.05; 4 = 9.49$

Questionnaire items 1, 4 and 9 were selected and used to represent others because they have the highest mean score calculation of 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4, respectively. Thus, they are the most accepted questions in the questionnaire items in their research question sections. Therefore, the Chi-square (X²) tabulated is 9.49.

Table 6: Hypothesis 1: The 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme does not significantly impact Anambra State's youth empowerment and sustainable development.

Impact of 'One Youth-Two Skills' scheme on youth empowerment and development in Anambra State.

Scale (1-5)	Observed Value (o)	Expected Value (e)	o-e	(o-e) ²	(o-e) ² /e
1	4	24	-20	400	16.6
2	9	24	-15	225	9.3
3	8	24	-16	256	10.6
4	33	24	9	81	3.3
5	66	24	42	1764	73.5
Total	120			Chi-Square	113.3
Exp. Value (Average)	24				

Source: *Authors' Field Survey Result, (2025).*

The chi-square calculated value exceeds the critical/tabulated value (**113.3 > 9.49**), which means the null (H₀) hypothesis that states that the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has no significant impact on the youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State was rejected, to accept the alternate (H₁) hypothesis that states that; One Youth-Two Skills’ has impacted on the youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State. Therefore, research question 1 has the highest means score with 4.2, i.e. it is the most accepted among others.

Table 7: Hypothesis 2: The ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has no strategies for achieving youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State.

Strategies of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme in Anambra State.					
Scale (1-5)	Observed Value (o)	Expected Value (e)	o-e	(o-e) ²	(o-e) ² /e
1	2	24	-22	484	20.1
2	2	24	-22	484	20.1
3	10	24	-14	196	10.6
4	47	24	23	529	8.1
5	59	24	35	1225	51.0
Total	120			Chi-Square	109.9
Exp. Value (Average)	24				

Source: *Authors' Field Survey Result, (2025).*

The chi-square calculated value is greater than the critical/tabulated value (**109.9 > 9.49**), which implies that the null (H₀) hypothesis that states that; ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has no strategies employed towards achieving youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State” was rejected to accept the alternate (H₁) hypothesis that states that ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has employed various strategies like effective transformational leadership with clear set goals, objectives and good management, etc. towards achieving youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State. Therefore, question 4 has the highest means score of 4.3, i.e. it is the most accepted among others.

Table 8: Hypothesis 3: No challenges face the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme on youth empowerment and development at Anambra State.

Challenges of ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ on Youth empowerment and sustainable development					
Scale (1-5)	Observed Value (o)	Expected Value (e)	o-e	(o-e)²	(o-e)²/e
1	2	24	-22	484	20.1
2	3	24	-21	441	18.3
3	7	24	-17	289	12.0
4	40	24	16	256	10.6
5	68	24	44	1936	80.6
Total	120			Chi-Square	141.6
Exp. Value (Average)	24				

Source: *Authors’ Field Survey Result, (2025).*

The chi-square Calculated value is more than the critical/tabulated value (**141.6 > 9.49**), which means the null (H₀) hypothesis states, “There are no challenges facing the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme on youth empowerment and development scheme at Anambra State,” was rejected to accept the alternative (H₁) hypothesis that states that; “There are challenges facing the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme on youth empowerment and development scheme at Anambra State. Therefore, question 9 has the highest mean score of 4.4, i.e. it is the most accepted among others.

Discussions

The study finds out that the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has affected your overall well-being, prospects and sustainable youth empowerment and development in Anambra State” with a grand mean score of 4.2. However, that One Youth-Two Skills scheme has impacted your ability to start and sustain your own business or entrepreneurial venture” with a grand mean score of 4.1. Thus, the One Youth-Two Skills scheme has increased skill acquisition, capacity building, knowledge and employability” with a grand means score of 4.0. However, this aligned with Rodney (1972) view on development at individual level, The effective transformational leadership with clearly set goals and good management has aided the success of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme, with a grand mean score of 4.3; the adequate funding and equitable resource allocation have contributed to the success of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme with a grand mean score of 4.1.

However, the partnership and collaborations with stakeholders and various institutions have helped the One Youth-Two Skills scheme with a grand mean score of 4.2. Moreover, insufficient funds and poor allocation of materials tend to affect the long-term sustainability of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme. Inadequate partnerships and collaboration with private sector organisations and institutions have limited the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’, and a lack of qualified/professional master’s trainers and poor monitoring affect the sustainability of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme. Thus, this is in support of World Bank (2017) advocacy for a good partnership and collaboration between states and international, local and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), The study finds out that the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme has significantly impacted youth empowerment and sustainable development in Anambra State by changing their overall well-being and prospects, the

ability to establish and sustain their business and entrepreneur ventures, increasing their skill acquisitions, capacity, and knowledge, creating job opportunities and making them employable(Aquino, 2018; Child Hope, 2023).

In a nutshell, the study further revealed that the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme in Anambra State was successful due to transformational leadership with clearly set goals and objectives, good management, funding and resource allocations, support, partnership and collaborations with agencies and institutions (World Bank, 2017). Therefore, insufficient funds and material allocation, inadequate partnerships and collaboration, lack of qualified/professional master’s trainers, poor monitoring and evaluation, etc., are the challenges facing the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme on youth empowerment and development at Anambra State.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study is focused on achieving youth empowerment and sustainable development through the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ program and offers significant insights into the capacity of such efforts to foster sustainable development in Anambra State, Nigeria. However, the study concluded that the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme is a solution-driven scheme that has benefited and positively impacted youths' ability to gain employment by establishing their businesses for their self-development and socioeconomic well-being. The high level of government support, funding/grants, strong leadership, and extensive collaboration/partnership contributed to the success of the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ scheme in Anambra State. A peaceful and stable nation depends significantly on the government (Chukwudi et al., 2019). Therefore, by executing the proposed measures, policymakers may augment the program's scope and efficacy, empowering the youth of Anambra State to become pivotal contributors to the state's socio-economic advancement and comprehensive sustainable development. The study made the following recommendations which are:

- a. Enhancement of the program through proper monitoring and evaluation, i.e., regular impact assessments, will be performed to monitor the long-term consequences of the program on youth employment, income levels, and social mobility. A data-driven monitoring system that evaluates participant performance post-training should be implemented to ensure that acquired skills result in substantial employment or entrepreneurial opportunities.
- b. To guarantee that the skills acquired in the program apply to the present labour market, the government should forge closer alliances, partnerships, and collaborations with renowned stakeholders in private industries, NGOs, and institutions to ensure that every youth acquires more than one skill.
- c. Government should broaden the range of skills provided, emphasising high-demand industries such as information technology, agriculture, renewable energy, and manufacturing. This would enhance the program's inclusivity and adaptability to changing market trends. However, a skill acquisition high-standard certification should be provided for both conventional and contemporary skills to enhance youths' credibility in the employment market.
 - a. There should be a reasonable increase in the fund, grant, or loan amount, as well as good working machines, appliances, and tools given to the youth trainees to enable them to start

their private businesses. Thus, the programme should always engage a team of certified professional master trainers to facilitate adequate training of young people. However, adequate screening should be conducted to engage only committed and open-minded youths ready to undergo such programme with seriousness and devoid of any other distractions.

Policy Implications and Relevance

The results of this study on the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ program in Anambra State, Nigeria, have important policy relevance that could influence further study for youth empowerment in line with the Sustainable Development Goals. The outcome of this study can help policymakers, stakeholders, NGOs and institutions to design and support skill-based education curricula and initiatives stressing the usefulness of talent innovation that will fit the present employment market; share programs like the ‘One Youth-Two Skills’ concept, among other Nigerian states, using Anambra State’s experience to guide youth empowerment and development initiatives, and establishes policies using business incubators, mentoring, and financial access that reward young entrepreneurship.

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Declaration Of Interest

None.

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